

Additional file 1.

Long read sequences from GenBank used to generate the *P. falciparum* *msp1* block 2 reference library

Accession numbers	No. of sequences	Reference
AB116596-AB116601	6	[1][1][1][1]
AB276001-AB276018, AB300615-AB300614	20	[2]
AB502443-AB502745, AB715435-AB715519	388	[3]
AB502746-AB502795	50	[4]
AB827737-AB827762	26	[5]
AF061119-AF061151	33	[6]
AF062348-AF062349	2	[7]
AF218248	1	[8]
AF462449-AF462456, AY826427-AY826431, DQ377133-DQ377137	18	[9]
AJ635200	1	[10]
AY714585-AY714586	2	[11]
DQ026701-DQ026702	2	[12]
DQ447647	1	[13]
DQ485417-DQ485451	35	[14]
DQ855130-DQ855135	5	[15]
EU032016-EU037095	262	[16]
HM153166-HM153256	91	[17]
HQ821869-HQ821872	4	[18]
JF300128	1	[19]
JX315617, JX412318-JX412322, JX416338-JX416341	9	[20]
KP318436-KP318438	3	[21]
KR063228-KR063231	4	[22]
L10380, M77713-M77737	26	[23]
M19143-M19144	2	[24]
M32111-M32116	6	[25]
M35727/Y00087	1	[26]
M37213	1	[27]
M55001	1	[28]
X02919	1	[29]
X03371	1	[30]
X03831	1	[31]
X05624	1	[32]
X15063	1	[33]
X52962-X52963	2	[34]
X61930	1	[35]
Z35327	1	[36]

GenBank was searched with the search terms: “*plasmodium falciparum* [organism] *msp1*”; “*plasmodium falciparum* [organism] *msa1*”; and “*plasmodium falciparum* [organism] *gp195*” on 4th December 2015. All sequences containing *msp1* block2 were downloaded. Duplicate sequences from the same laboratory strain were removed leaving 964 sequences (Additional file 2). The GenBank accession numbers for the sequences are shown with the number of sequences and the reference for the study for which they were produced.

References

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